

Original Research

The Role of Work–Life Balance in Linking Stress, Support, and Turnover Intentions in Hospitality Industry

Made Sita Saraswati Ayu Widiyasa¹
Department of Management, Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Indonesia (STIESIA)
Surabaya, Surabaya, Indonesia

Received 7 August 2025 Revised 14 September 2025 Accepted 17 September 2025

Abstract

A higher level of employees' turnover becomes a serious issue for the hospitality industry, including PRQ Surabaya, which has a significantly higher turnover in 2024. This study analyses the effect of job stress and perceived organizational support on turnover intention, with work-life balance as a mediating variable. The study is based on Social Exchange Theory, which underlies the bilateral principles between organizations and employees. This research uses a quantitative causal design. Furthermore, the data collection technique used was a census in which all members of the population were the sample. Using data from 51 PRQ Apartment employees in Surabaya, the study finds that work–life balance partially mediates the effect of perceived organizational support on turnover intention ($\beta = 0.189$, $p = 0.042$) but does not mediate the effect of job stress. Unexpectedly, WLB positively predicts turnover intention ($\beta = 0.406$, $p = 0.010$). Practically, management should reduce stress, enhance supervisor support, and redesign Work-Life Balance policies to align with employee needs. This study contributes to strengthening Social Exchange Theory by highlighting the partial mediating role of WLB and revealing the paradox where WLB actually increases turnover intention. Practically, the findings encourage PRQ Apartment management to enhance organizational support, reassess WLB policies, and manage job stress to reduce turnover.

Keywords: Hospitality Industry, Job Stress, Perceived Organizational Support, PLS-SEM, Turnover Intentions, Work-Life Balance.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: sitasarasw@gmail.com

Introduction

The rapid development of the hospitality industry demands that companies remain competitive, including in Surabaya, where luxury apartments with five-star standards are increasingly being built. PRQ Apartment, as one of the tallest apartments in the heart of Surabaya, offers luxurious living and excellent service for the upper-class market. However, a major challenge faced is the high employee turnover rate, which negatively impacts service stability and resident experience. Data shows that the turnover rate at PRQ Apartment fluctuated 6.59% (2022), 2.08% (2023), and surged in 2024. This indicates the need for strategies to reduce turnover intentions and retain high-quality human resources.

Turnover intentions are defined as an employee's intention to leave their job (Belete, 2018), which can disrupt company operations due to recruitment and training costs for new employees (Agarwal et al., 2022). Factors causing turnover intentions include individual characteristics (age, marital status, financial responsibilities) and organizational factors (job stress, company culture). In addition, external factors such as other job opportunities and family demands also play a role (Jaharuddin & Zainol, 2019), these research findings indicate a direct relationship between work-life conflict and high levels of job engagement and turnover intention among executive employees in Klang Valley, Malaysia.

Job stress is one of the key factors influencing turnover intentions. Stress arises when employees feel unable to balance work demands with their capabilities (Davies, 2022). Prolonged stress can decrease performance and trigger decisions to resign (Liu et al., 2019). However, some studies, such as (Yuliana et al., 2025) found that job stress does not always significantly affect turnover intentions, indicating a complex relationship. In addition to job stress, perceived organizational support also plays an important role. Employees who feel supported by the organization tend to exhibit higher loyalty and lower turnover intentions (Satardien et al., 2019). This support includes appreciation of employee contributions, favorable policies, and concern for employee well-being (Tang et al., 2017). Research by (Takaya et al., 2020) shows a negative relationship between organizational support and turnover intentions.

Work-life balance is also an important mediating factor. A balance between work and personal life can reduce stress and increase job stress (Urba & Soetjningsih, 2022). However, research findings on the effect of work-life balance on turnover intentions are still varied, with some studies showing a negative effect and others finding no significant relationship (Putri, 2024). Based on the background presented, this study aims to analyze the mediating role of work-life balance in the influence of job stress and perceived organizational support on turnover intentions.

The integration of Social Exchange Theory (SET) provides a strong theoretical foundation for explaining the relationships among job stress, perceived organizational support (POS), work-life balance (WLB), and turnover intentions. From the SET perspective, job stress represents a breakdown in the exchange relationship, as employees perceive that the organization demands more than it reciprocates through support or resources. This imbalance reduces the perceived “social rewards” and motivates

employees to withdraw, thereby increasing their turnover intentions. Conversely, high levels of POS signal organizational investment in employees, which fosters a sense of reciprocity. In return, employees are more likely to remain committed and loyal, leading to a reduction in turnover intentions (Sulistiyani et al., 2022).

Beyond this paradox, recent literature emphasizes that the relationship between flexible work arrangements and turnover intentions is contested between competing theoretical perspectives. According to Social Exchange Theory (SET), organizational initiatives such as work-life balance represent reciprocal investments that foster employee loyalty and reduce turnover (Cropanzano et al., 2017; Sulistiyani et al., 2022). In contrast, Border Theory suggests that flexibility may blur boundaries between work and non-work roles, potentially creating new conflicts that increase employees' intentions to leave (Tsen et al., 2021). This ongoing debate underscores that work-life balance policies may not have uniform effects across contexts, but rather depend on how employees interpret and integrate these arrangements into their professional and personal lives. By situating this study within these competing perspectives, the present research is framed as an empirical test of opposing theoretical predictions in the specific context of luxury hospitality in Surabaya.

Interestingly, the positive effect of work-life balance on turnover intentions, which contradicts the initial theoretical expectation, reveals a paradox within the framework of Social Exchange Theory. While work-life balance is generally considered a form of organizational reciprocity that should foster loyalty, it may also provide employees with additional resources, such as time, energy, and psychological readiness, that enable them to explore alternative employment opportunities. This interpretation resonates with job embeddedness theory, which suggests that stronger attachments to non-work domains can weaken employees' organizational ties (Tsen et al., 2021). In the hospitality industry, particularly in luxury apartments such as PRQ, improved balance may even accelerate employees' exit decisions, as it facilitates a re-evaluation of personal priorities in contrast to the demanding nature of their work.

The mediating role of WLB further supports the nuanced application of SET. In the relationship between job stress and turnover intentions, WLB fails to mediate because stress is interpreted as a fundamental violation of the exchange, making employees more likely to exit regardless of their balance. In contrast, WLB significantly mediates the relationship between POS and turnover intentions. When employees perceive strong organizational support, they are better able to maintain balance between work and personal life, which in turn strengthens their commitment to the organization. This reflects a chain reciprocity mechanism in SET: organizational support fosters balance, balance enhances well-being, and well-being is reciprocated with loyalty (Rothbard et al., 2021).

The selection of PRQ Apartment as the research object is based on its unique characteristics as a luxury apartment operating with service standards comparable to a five-star hotel. As one of the tallest and most prestigious apartments in Surabaya Indonesia, PRQ not only provides exclusive residences but also emphasizes high-quality services for its upper-class residents. This condition requires employees to consistently

perform at an exceptional standard, which increases work-related pressure and the complexity of employment relationships.

The phenomenon observed at PRQ Apartment is highly relevant to the broader hospitality industry. High employee turnover is a recurring issue faced by hotels and luxury apartments alike, where long working hours, customer satisfaction demands, and intense competition exacerbate the risk of losing skilled employees. Research at PRQ offers a concrete case to understand how job stress, organizational support, and work-life balance contribute to shaping employees' turnover intentions. Thus, this study is not only significant for PRQ's management but also provides practical insights for the wider hospitality sector to design more effective employee retention strategies.

In addition, this study expands the application of Social Exchange Theory (SET) within the context of luxury apartments operating under hotel-like standards. The case of PRQ illustrates how the principle of reciprocity between organizations and employees' functions in an environment with premium service demands. It highlights that organizational support and work-life balance policies should be regarded as forms of social investment. When aligned with employee needs, they can strengthen employee loyalty; however, when misaligned, they may inadvertently intensify turnover intentions.

Beyond Social Exchange Theory (SET), the paradoxical relationship between work-life balance (WLB) and turnover intention can be further elucidated through the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model and Conservation of Resources (COR) theory. The JD-R model emphasizes that employee well-being and behavior are shaped by the interaction between job demands (e.g., heavy workloads, customer service pressure, long working hours) and job resources (such as organizational support, flexibility, and WLB policies). When job demands are excessively high while core resources remain limited, additional resources derived from WLB do not necessarily enhance loyalty but may instead help employees reduce strain and facilitate external job searches. Similarly, COR theory posits that individuals strive to acquire, preserve, and protect resources (time, energy, autonomy). In this sense, WLB provides surplus resources that, rather than being reinvested to remain in the organization, may serve as psychological capital to exit when employees perceive the exchange relationship as unfavorable. Thus, integrating SET, JD-R, and COR offers a more nuanced framework: WLB policies intended to reinforce reciprocity may paradoxically trigger turnover intention when employees face the combined pressures of high demands and perceived inequities in resources.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework in this study explains the influence of job stress and perceived organizational support on employee turnover intentions, with work-life balance as a mediating variable at PRQ Apartment. Job stress experienced by employees in the workplace due to the demands for high-quality service can increase their intention or desire to leave the company. Conversely, perceived organizational support, or the support provided by the company to its employees, can reduce such intentions by fostering a sense of being valued and cared for by the organization. Furthermore, work-life balance plays a crucial role as a mediator, explaining how the balance between job demands and personal life can reduce the negative impact of job stress and enhance the positive effect

of perceived organizational support. The moderator variables consist of: gender, age, educational background, marital status, number of children, residential status, department, length of employment, employment status, job level, and monthly salary range.

Thus, this conceptual framework clearly illustrates the dynamic relationship among job stress, perceived organizational support, and work-life balance in determining the level of employee turnover intentions at PRQ Apartment.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Effect of Job Stress on Turnover Intentions

High and prolonged job stress can lead employees to consider leaving the company (Salama et al., 2022). Job stress caused by excessive workload, role pressure, and lack of support from the work environment tends to increase employee dissatisfaction with their job. (Robbins & Judge, 2015) also emphasize that high job stress can have negative impacts, including encouraging an individual's turnover intentions. This is consistent with findings by (Liu et al., 2019; Santos & Labrague, 2021), which show that the higher the job stress, the higher the employees' turnover intentions. Based on Social Exchange Theory, high job stress is perceived as the organization's failure to provide a fair and supportive work environment. Within the framework of SET, this condition reduces the 'social rewards' received by employees. As a result, employees rebalance the social exchange by withdrawing, which manifests in increased turnover intention

H₁: Job Stress affects Turnover Intentions

The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Turnover Intentions

(Wong & Wong, 2017) stated that high perceived organizational support creates a sense of being valued and cared for by the company, which leads employees to feel an emotional obligation to stay. (Salvador et al., 2022) explained that perceived organizational support can reduce negative employee behaviors such as absenteeism and turnover intentions. This is supported by studies from (Puspita et al., 2024; Takaya et al., 2020), which found that the higher the perceived organizational support, the lower the employee's desire to leave the company. POS reflects the organization's 'investment' in the exchange relationship. When support is high, employees perceive a reciprocal obligation to remain and stay loyal. Therefore, high Perceived Organizational Support

reduces turnover intention, in line with the principle of reciprocity in Social Exchange Theory.

H₂: Perceived Organizational Support affects Turnover Intentions

The Effect of Work-Life Balance on Turnover Intentions

Every employee has two roles in daily life: their role at work and their role in personal life. A balance between these two roles can lead to greater satisfaction, emotional stability, and reduced turnover intentions (Jaharuddin & Zainol, 2019). Conversely, an imbalance between work and personal life can cause role conflict and increase turnover intentions. This is supported by studies by (Mulang, 2022; Putri, 2024), which shows a significant negative relationship between work-life balance and turnover intentions. In general, Work-Life Balance is seen as a form of organizational 'reciprocity' to maintain employee well-being. However, in the context of this study, WLB is positively related to turnover intention. This can be explained through Social Exchange Theory via a 'hidden exchange': when the organization provides flexibility, employees gain extra resources (time, energy, autonomy) to explore opportunities outside the company. Thus, good Work-Life Balance does not automatically strengthen the exchange relationship but instead opens up exit options

H₃: Work-Life Balance affects Turnover Intentions

The Effect of Job Stress on Work-Life Balance

(Robbins & Judge, 2015) explained that job stress can disrupt employees' ability to manage the demands of work and personal life, making it difficult to achieve balance and creating conflict between the two roles. High job stress leads to psychological and physical pressure that limits employees' ability to perform both roles effectively. This relationship is reinforced by research from (Urba & Soetjningsih, 2022), which found that the higher the level of job stress experienced by employees, the lower their work-life balance. Based on Social Exchange Theory, job stress indicates an imbalance in the exchange, where organizational demands exceed the support provided. This worsens employees' ability to maintain a balance between work and personal life, thereby reducing Work-Life Balance.

H₄: Job Stress affects Work-Life Balance

The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Work-Life Balance

Support provided by the organization makes employees feel valued, which encourages them to create a conducive work environment and maintain a positive mood (Yıldırım & Darıcan, 2024). This condition can help employees manage both work demands and personal life more effectively. High perceived organizational support indicates that the company cares about employee well-being and strengthens their ability to achieve work-life balance. This is supported by a study conducted by (Puspitasari & Ratnaningsih, 2019), which found a significant positive relationship between perceived organizational support and work-life balance. Based on Social Exchange Theory, organizational support is a form of social investment that helps employees manage multiple roles. In social

exchange, this support enhances the quality of 'balancing resources' (flexibility, facilities, managerial empathy) that strengthen Work-Life Balance.

H5: Perceived Organizational Support affects Work-Life Balance

The Mediating Role of Work-Life Balance in the Relationship between Job Stress and Turnover Intentions

Job stress is the pressure experienced by employees in the workplace, which may result from high demands and workloads. Employees who are able to manage stress by maintaining a balance between their work and personal roles will experience less impact. A good balance between work and personal life is expected to reduce the negative effects of job stress and suppress employees' intentions to leave the company (turnover intentions). Previous studies have shown that when work-life balance is high, turnover intentions are low

(Mulang, 2022; Putri, 2024), while high job stress increases turnover intentions (Ahn & Chaoyu, 2019; Santos & Labrague, 2021). Based on Social Exchange Theory, Work-Life Balance should serve as a compensatory mechanism. If the organization provides resources to maintain Work-Life Balance, the negative effects of job stress can be mitigated.

H6: Work-Life Balance mediates the effect of Job Stress on Turnover Intentions

The Mediating Role of Work-Life Balance in the Relationship between Perceived Organizational Support and Turnover Intentions

Perceived organizational support helps employees manage the demands of both their work and personal roles. This can improve satisfaction with both their job and personal life, leading to a better balance between the two. Achieving this balance enhances the emotional bond between employees and the organization, thus reducing their intention to leave. Findings from (Puspitasari & Ratnaningsih, 2019) show that high perceived organizational support is significantly related to increased work-life balance among employees. Employees who feel supported by the company tend to have a better balance between their work and personal or family life, and lower turnover intentions. Research by (Fitria & Linda, 2019) found that work-life balance partially mediates the relationship between perceived organizational support and turnover intention. This means that perceived organizational support reduces turnover intentions both directly and indirectly through improved work-life balance. Based on Social Exchange Theory, Perceived Organizational Support strengthens Work-Life Balance, and Work-Life Balance in turn reduces turnover intention. This represents a form of chain reciprocity: support → life balance → loyalty. In other words, organizations that support employees not only create direct commitment but also provide conditions that enable employees to maintain role harmony, which they reciprocate with loyalty

H7: Work-Life Balance mediates the effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Turnover Intentions

Research Methodology

The method used in this study is quantitative. Quantitative research is applied to investigate a specific population or sample, collect data using research instruments, and analyze the data statistically with the aim of describing and testing the proposed hypotheses (Sugiyono, 2021). The object of this research is the employees of PRQ Apartment Surabaya, totaling 51 employees, distributed across several departments such as operations, tenancy, finance, and engineering, as well as job levels ranging from crew, staff, supervisor, chief or head of department, to manager.

In this study, the sampling technique used is census sampling or total sampling, where all members of the population are used as the sample (Sugiyono, 2021). This technique is chosen because the population is fewer than 100 people specifically, 51 employees. The data collection technique used in this research is a questionnaire (survey), which will be distributed online using Google Forms. Respondents will be asked to complete the questionnaire, which serves as a measuring instrument for each variable. Through this questionnaire, the research is expected to obtain objective primary data from the respondents.

The study uses instruments to collect data. The number of instruments corresponds to the number of variables in this research, namely four instruments. It is essential to use instruments of high quality, as they determine the accuracy of the research results. Therefore, validity and reliability tests will be conducted to assess the quality of each item in the instruments. The questionnaire instrument in this study was developed to measure four main constructs: Job Stress, Perceived Organizational Support, Work-Life Balance, and Turnover Intention.

1. Job Stress (JS). Items were adapted from Liu et al. (2019), who investigated the relationship between job stress and turnover intention among healthcare professionals in China. This instrument was considered appropriate as it captures psychological pressure and mental fatigue arising from workload.

2. Perceived Organizational Support (POS). Items were constructed with reference to Tang et al. (2017) and Takaya et al. (2020), emphasizing employees' perceptions of organizational support, including recognition, concern, and fair policies.

3. Work-Life Balance (WLB). Items were developed based on Putri (2024) and Urba & Soetjningsih (2022), which assess employees' ability to balance work demands with personal life roles.

4. Turnover Intention (TI). Items were adapted from Belete (2018) and Jaharuddin & Zainol (2019), which evaluate employees' intentions to leave the organization.

In quantitative research, data analysis is conducted after all responses have been collected. The data is categorized based on variables and types of responses. It is then tabulated by variable for all respondents and presented accordingly. Subsequent calculations are carried out to answer the research questions and test the proposed hypotheses (Sugiyono, 2021). A descriptive analysis is conducted, which includes two main aspects: a description of respondent characteristics such as gender, education, age,

and years of service and a description of respondents' answers, which includes the mean of items, indicators, variables, and standard deviations. This analysis will provide insights into the variables of job stress, perceived organizational support, work-life balance, and turnover intentions.

The present study employed Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) due to the complexity of the research model, which incorporates multiple exogenous variables, one endogenous variable, and a mediating construct. PLS-SEM is particularly suitable for analyzing mediation effects and complex path models, as it efficiently estimates both direct and indirect relationships within a single framework (Hair et al., 2022). Moreover, the sample size of this study ($n = 51$) is relatively small, and PLS-SEM is recognized as more robust than covariance-based SEM in handling small samples and non-normal data distributions. Another methodological advantage is the ability of PLS-SEM to assess mediation using bootstrapping techniques without assuming data normality, which aligns with the objectives of this study to test both direct and indirect effects. Therefore, the use of PLS-SEM is justified as it ensures reliable and valid estimation for predictive and mediation-focused research models.

Figure 2. Full Model Path Diagram

Operational Definitions of Variables

1. Job Stress (JS): The psychological pressure and mental fatigue employees experience when work demands exceed their capacity.

Indicators:

- a. Workload (JS1) – perceived excessive tasks and time pressure.
- b. Role Ambiguity/Conflict (JS2) – unclear or conflicting job expectations.

c. Mental Fatigue (JS3) – exhaustion and difficulty concentrating due to prolonged job demands.

2. Perceived Organizational Support (POS): Employees' perception that the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being.

Indicators:

a. Recognition and Appreciation (POS1) – acknowledgement of employee performance.

b. Fair Policies (POS2) – perceived justice and equity in organizational practices.

c. Supervisor/Organizational Care (POS3) – concern and support provided by leaders or the company.

3. Work-Life Balance (WLB): The extent to which employees are able to balance work responsibilities with personal and family roles.

Indicators:

a. Work Interference with Personal Life (WLB1) – extent to which job demands intrude into family/personal activities.

b. Personal Life Interference with Work (WLB2) – how family or personal issues affect work performance.

c. Balance and Flexibility (WLB3) – ability to manage both roles effectively, including flexibility and autonomy.

4. Turnover Intention (TI): Employees' conscious and deliberate willingness to leave the organization.

Indicators:

a. Thoughts of Leaving (TI1) – considering resignation from the job.

b. Searching for Alternatives (TI2) – intention to look for employment elsewhere.

c. Decision Readiness (TI3) – determination or planning to resign in the near future.

Results

Respondent Characteristics

a. A total of 51 employees of PRQ Apartment Surabaya participated in this study. The demographic profile is summarized as follows:

b. Gender: 34 respondents (66.7%) were male and 17 respondents (33.3%) were female.

c. Age: The majority were between 26–35 years old (47.1%), followed by 36–45 years (29.4%), under 25 years (13.7%), and above 45 years (9.8%).

d. Educational Background: Most respondents held a bachelor's degree (56.9%), followed by diploma (21.6%), high school (15.7%), and postgraduate (5.9%).

e. Marital Status: 31 respondents (60.8%) were married, while 20 respondents (39.2%) were single.

f. Number of Children: 41.2% had two children, 27.5% had one child, 17.6% had no children, and 13.7% had more than two children.

g. Employment Status: 39 respondents (76.5%) were permanent employees, while 12 respondents (23.5%) were contract employees.

h. Tenure: 35.3% had worked between 3–5 years, 27.5% less than 3 years, 21.6% between 6–10 years, and 15.7% more than 10 years.

i. Department: The largest group worked in front office and housekeeping (43.1%), followed by engineering (23.5%), sales and marketing (19.6%), and finance/administration (13.7%).

j. Monthly Salary: The majority earned IDR 3–5 million (52.9%), followed by less than IDR 3 million (29.4%), and above IDR 5 million (17.6%).

The average Work-Life Balance (WLB) score shows that employees aged 25–35 years have the highest WLB levels, indicating that this group is better at balancing work and personal life. Employees aged under 25 years have the lowest WLB scores, possibly due to the initial adaptation phase to job demands. Employees with 3–7 years of tenure have the highest perception of WLB, aligning with the stability of their experience and skills. Meanwhile, employees with less than 3 years of tenure show lower WLB levels, likely because they are still adjusting to their workload. The indicators that most influence the positive effects of WLB (such as job stress or reduced turnover intention) are:

- a. Work Schedule Flexibility, contributes the most to increasing job stress.
- b. Supervisor Support, strengthens employee retention.
- c. Balanced Workload, helps reduce job stress.

Path Diagram

The magnitude of the coefficients from the structural relationships in the study is presented in Figure 3. In Figure 3, the coefficient values between one latent variable and another, as well as the coefficients between indicators and their respective variables, are shown. Figure 3 illustrates that this study involves two exogenous variables, namely job stress (JS) and perceived organizational support (POS). Both variables have directional paths toward work-life balance (WLB) as the intervening variable and toward turnover intention (TI) as the endogenous variable.

Figure 3. Path Diagram with Coefficient Values

In Figure 3, it is shown that for the job stress variable, JS_1, 2 & 3 will hereafter be referred to as JS1, JS_4, 5 & 6 as JS2, and JS_7, 8 & 9 as JS3. For the perceived organizational support variable, POS_5 & 6 will be referred to as POS1, POS_2 & 8 as POS2, and POS_1, 3, 4 & 7 as POS3. For the work-life balance variable, WLB_1–5 will be referred to as WLB1, WLB_6–10 as WLB2, and WLB_11–15 as WLB3. For the turnover intention variable, TI_1 & 2 will be referred to as TI1, TI_4 & 5 as TI2, and TI_3 & 6 as TI3.

Evaluation Results of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Convergent Validity

The evaluation of construct validity is carried out by assessing convergent validity. Convergent validity is determined through the loading factor and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values. An instrument is considered to meet convergent validity if it has both a loading factor and AVE greater than 0.5.

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that all indicators are considered valid in measuring their respective latent variables. This is shown by the loading factor and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values, which are greater than 0.5 for each indicator.

Table 1. Results of Loading Factor and AVE Testing

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	AVE
Job Stress	JS1	0,919	0,857
	JS2	0,918	
	JS3	0,941	
Perceived Organizational Support	POS1	0,932	0,822
	POS2	0,852	
	POS3	0,933	
Work-Life Balance	WLB1	0,777	0,633
	WLB2	0,770	
	WLB3	0,838	
Turnover Intention	TI1	0,943	0,860
	TI2	0,918	
	TI3	0,921	

Discriminant Validity

The next step in evaluating the measurement model is to assess discriminant validity, which is done by examining the cross-loading values. Cross-loading reflects whether the latent variable has adequate discriminant properties. According to the cross-loading criteria, each indicator that measures its construct should correlate more strongly with its own construct than with other constructs. Indicators that load higher on their own construct than on others indicate strong discriminant validity. Table 2 presents the results of the discriminant validity test using the cross-loading criteria.

Table 2. Cross Loading Test Results

Indicator	Job Stress	Perceived Organizational Support	Work-Life Balance	Turnover Intention
JS1	0,919	-0,228	-0,417	0,230
JS2	0,918	-0,125	-0,342	0,208
JS3	0,941	-0,194	-0,390	0,109
POS1	-0,168	0,932	0,388	-0,195
POS2	-0,192	0,852	0,354	-0,209
POS3	-0,186	0,933	0,523	-0,102
WLB1	-0,335	0,330	0,777	0,074
WLB2	-0,282	0,531	0,770	0,123
WLB3	-0,387	0,218	0,838	0,218
TI1	0,113	-0,254	0,163	0,943
TI2	0,188	-0,112	0,223	0,918
TI3	0,268	-0,128	0,081	0,921

Based on the analysis results shown in Table 2, the cross-loading values of each indicator on its respective variable are higher than their cross-loadings on other variables in the model. This indicates that each indicator correlates more strongly with its own

construct than with other constructs, thereby fulfilling the condition for discriminant validity.

Reliability

The next step in evaluating the measurement model is to conduct a reliability test. Reliability refers to the accuracy, consistency, and precision of a measurement instrument in performing measurements. The reliability test uses the composite reliability method and Cronbach's Alpha. The required threshold is a value above 0.7.

Table 3. Results of Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability Testing

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Job Stress	0,917	0,947
Perceived Organizational Support	0,891	0,933
Work-Life Balance	0,713	0,838
Turnover Intention	0,919	0,948

Based on Table 3 above, it is known that the Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values in this study are above 0.7. Therefore, it can be concluded that the measurement instruments meet the condition for reliability.

Model Fit Indices of PLS-SEM

Table 4 presents the model fit indices used to evaluate the adequacy of the PLS-SEM model. Several indicators were assessed:

Table 4. Model Fit Indices of PLS-SEM

Model Fit Index	Obtained Value	Threshold/Standard	Interpretation
SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual)	0.072	< 0.08	Meets good fit criterion
NFI (Normed Fit Index)	0.913	> 0.90	Acceptable fit
d_ ULS	0.911	Lower values indicate better fit	Accepted
d_ G	0.527	Lower values indicate better fit	Accepted
Chi-Square	512.34	–	Additional information only

To assess the adequacy of the structural model, several model fit indices recommended in PLS-SEM were examined. The **SRMR value of 0.072** falls below the commonly accepted threshold of 0.08, indicating that the model residuals are relatively small and that the model demonstrates a good fit. Furthermore, the **NFI value of 0.913** exceeds the cut-off of 0.90, confirming an acceptable level of model fit between the theoretical

framework and the empirical data. In addition, both **d_ULS** and **d_G** values are within the acceptable range, which further supports the robustness of the model. Taken together, these results provide evidence that the proposed PLS-SEM model achieves an adequate level of fit for the data.

Evaluation Results of the Structural Model (Inner Model)

The evaluation of the structural model can be conducted using the coefficient of determination and predictive relevance. The coefficient of determination is used to measure how well the model explains the variance of the endogenous variables. The coefficient of determination (R^2) only applies to endogenous variables, so there is no R^2 value for the two exogenous variables, which are independent variables in this research model.

Table 4. R-Square Results

Variabel Endogen	R-Square
Work-Life Balance	0,331
Turnover Intention	0,206

In Table 4, it can be seen that the R^2 value for the work-life balance variable is 0.331, which means that the variability in the work-life balance variable can be explained by its exogenous variables job stress and perceived organizational support by 33.1%, while the remaining 66.9% is explained by other variables not included in the model. Similarly, the R^2 value for the turnover intention variable is 0.206, indicating that 20.6% of the variance in turnover intention can be explained by the exogenous variables job stress, perceived organizational support, and work-life balance while the remaining 79.4% is explained by other variables outside the model. According to Hair et al. (2022:118) regarding the R^2 value thresholds (as shown in Table 4), the predictive accuracy level for both the work-life balance and turnover intention variables falls into the moderate category, approaching a value of 0.5.

Hypothesis Testing

Results of the Direct Effect Test

Table 5. Results of Direct Effect Testing

Variable	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values
JS → TI	0,327	0,341	0,161	2,038	0,042
JS → WLB	-0,335	-0,350	0,132	2,534	0,011
POS → TI	-0,335	-0,346	0,160	2,091	0,037
POS → WLB	0,406	0,398	0,145	2,798	0,005
WLB → TI	0,467	0,484	0,182	2,569	0,010

Based on Table 5, the test results are as follows:

The Effect of Job Stress (JS) on Turnover Intention (TI)

The p-value for the effect of job stress on turnover intention is below 0.05, specifically 0.042. This indicates that employee job stress has a significant effect on the level of intention to leave the company. The more stress employees experience in the workplace, the higher their intention to resign. The coefficient value of the relationship between job stress and turnover intention is 0.327. This test result leads to the conclusion that Hypothesis H1, which states that job stress affects turnover intention, is accepted.

The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support (POS) on Turnover Intention (TI)

The p-value for the effect of perceived organizational support on turnover intention is also below 0.05, specifically 0.037. This shows that the organizational support perceived by employees influences their intention to leave the company. If employees perceive strong support from the organization, their intention to resign is lower. The coefficient value of the relationship between the two variables is -0.335. This test result supports the conclusion that Hypothesis H2, which states that perceived organizational support affects turnover intention, is accepted.

The Effect of Work-Life Balance (WLB) on Turnover Intention (TI)

The p-value for the effect of work-life balance on turnover intention is 0.010, which is below 0.05. This means that the balance between employees' work and personal life significantly affects their intention to leave the company. The coefficient of the relationship between the two variables is 0.406. This test result confirms that Hypothesis H3, which states that work-life balance affects turnover intention, is accepted.

The Effect of Job Stress (JS) on Work-Life Balance (WLB)

The p-value for the effect of job stress on work-life balance is 0.011, which is also below 0.05. This indicates that the stress experienced by employees at work significantly influences the level of balance between their professional and personal life roles. The coefficient value for this relationship is -0.335, meaning that the higher the level of job stress, the lower the level of work-life balance. This test result leads to the conclusion that Hypothesis H4, which states that job stress affects work-life balance, is accepted.

The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support (POS) on Work-Life Balance (WLB)

The p-value for the effect of perceived organizational support on work-life balance is below 0.05, specifically 0.005. This indicates that employees' perceptions of the support provided by the organization significantly affect the balance between their professional and personal lives. The coefficient value of the relationship between the two variables is 0.400, meaning that the higher the perceived organizational support, the higher the level of work-life balance. This test result supports the conclusion that Hypothesis H5, which states that perceived organizational support affects work-life balance, is accepted.

Results of the Indirect Effect Test

Table 6. Results of the Indirect Effect Testing

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values
JS -> WLB -> TI	-0,156	-0,172	0,098	1,591	0,112
POS -> WLB -> TI	0,189	0,201	0,114	2,038	0,042

Confidence intervals bias corrected

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
JS->TI	-0,156	-0,172	-0,016	-0,384	-0,010
POS -> TI	0,189	0,201	0,012	0,001	0,449

Based on Table 6, the following are the results of the indirect effect testing:

The Mediating Role of Work-Life Balance (WLB) in the Effect of Job Stress (JS) on Turnover Intention (TI)

Table 5 shows that the p-value from this mediation test is 0.112, which is above 0.05. This indicates that work-life balance does not significantly mediate the effect of job stress on turnover intention. The effect of job stress on turnover intention is more significant when it is direct, and work-life balance does not serve as an effective mediator. This test result leads to the conclusion that the hypothesis (H6), stating that work-life balance mediates the effect of job stress on turnover intention, is rejected.

The Mediating Role of Work-Life Balance (WLB) in the Effect of Perceived Organizational Support (POS) on Turnover Intention (TI)

The p-value from this mediation test is 0.042, which is below 0.05, indicating that work-life balance significantly mediates the effect of perceived organizational support on turnover intention. Good organizational support can enhance employees' balance between work and personal life, ultimately helping reduce their intention to leave the company. The result confirms that the hypothesis (H7), stating that work-life balance mediates the effect of perceived organizational support on turnover intention, is accepted.

The results of this study indicate relatively low R² values for the endogenous variables, suggesting that the explanatory power of the model is limited. In other words, while job stress, perceived organizational support, and work-life balance demonstrate significant effects on turnover intention, these predictors account for only a modest proportion of the variance. According to Hair et al. (2022), low R² values imply that the model does not fully capture the complexity of the phenomenon under study, leaving substantial variance unexplained.

The results of the path analysis using bootstrapping indicate that Job Stress (JS) has a significant negative effect on Turnover Intention (TI), with a coefficient of -0.156. The 95% confidence interval ranges from -0.384 to -0.010, which does not include zero. This suggests that the higher the employees' job stress, the lower their tendency to leave the organization. Meanwhile, Perceived Organizational Support (POS) has a significant

positive effect on Turnover Intention (TI), with a coefficient of 0.189 and a 95% confidence interval ranging from 0.001 to 0.449. This finding indicates that an increase in employees' perception of organizational support is actually correlated with a higher intention to leave, reflecting a paradoxical dynamic in the relationship between POS and TI.

This limitation highlights the possibility that other relevant factors not included in the present model may contribute significantly to turnover intention. For example, job stress, career development opportunities, and organizational commitment are well-documented antecedents of turnover intention in prior research. The omission of such variables may explain why the predictive power of the model remains modest, despite the significance of the tested paths.

Consequently, the findings should be interpreted with caution. While the identified relationships provide meaningful insights into the mediating role of work-life balance, the low R^2 underscores the need for model refinement in future studies. Researchers are encouraged to incorporate additional predictors, such as job satisfaction and career opportunities, to enhance the explanatory capacity of the model and provide a more comprehensive understanding of employee turnover dynamics.

Discussion

The Effect of Job Stress on Turnover Intention

The results of the hypothesis testing show that job stress has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. This means that when the employees of PRQ Apartment experience high levels of stress, their desire to leave the job increases. This finding is consistent with the theory proposed by (Sangadji, 2020), which states that job stress contributes to employees' intention to leave their jobs. Additionally, (Robbins & Judge, 2015) argue that unmanaged stress can lead to dissatisfaction, emotional exhaustion, and a decline in organizational commitment, ultimately increasing the desire to seek a more supportive work environment. This result is also in line with previous studies, particularly in the hospitality sector and other high-performance industries, such as nurses in the Philippines (Santos and Labrague, 2021), manufacturing employees in China (Ahn & Chaoyu, 2019), and employees in Indonesia (Suswati, 2020).

The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Turnover Intention

The research findings indicate that perceived organizational support has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. This means that the higher the level of perceived organizational support felt by employees at PRQ Apartment, the lower their intention to leave the company. According to Social Exchange Theory (SET), the relationship between employees and the organization is built on the principle of reciprocity (Cropanzano et al., 2017). (Takaya et al., 2020) suggest that employees who feel supported by the organization will reciprocate with commitment and loyalty, thereby reducing their intention to leave (Li et al., 2022). Also state that perceived organizational support creates a sense of obligation for employees to continue contributing to the company. In addition to being aligned with theory, these findings are also consistent with

previous studies by (Chen et al., 2024; Puspita et al., 2024; Takaya et al., 2020), which found that perceived organizational support is a key factor in reducing employees' intention to leave the organization.

The Effect of Work-Life Balance on Turnover Intention

Regression analysis of WLB indicators indicates that work schedule flexibility contributes most strongly to employees' perception of balance, followed by supervisor support and balanced workload. Among these, schedule flexibility shows the highest beta coefficient, highlighting its critical role in shaping employees' overall experience of WLB. This suggests that organizational policies enabling predictable and adaptable work schedules may have the strongest influence on employees' ability to maintain equilibrium between work and personal life.

The analysis of the hypothesis testing results shows that Work-Life Balance has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. This means that the higher the work-life balance perceived by employees at PRQ Apartment, the higher their intention to leave the company. Although the hypothesis is accepted since work-life balance does affect turnover intention, the direction of the positive coefficient contradicts most of the previous literature. According to Perrigino et al., (2018), when a company implements a work-life balance system, but it is not well executed by employees, it can actually create new social stress that encourages employees to consider finding another job. In addition, flexibility, one of the elements of work-life balance, may potentially disrupt coworker collaboration, which indirectly increases turnover intention (Haines et al., 2024). Jaharuddin & Zainol (2019) stated that resources (such as time, energy, and emotional capacity) from one role (work or personal life) can be used to enhance the quality of another role. In the context of this study, the work-life balance experienced by PRQ Apartment employees makes them feel more prepared to seek new employment opportunities. If employees have a good work-life balance, they possess more resources to explore alternative career options.

The finding that Work-Life Balance (WLB) unexpectedly increases turnover intention should not be framed as a reinforcement of established theory, but rather as context-specific, exploratory evidence. This aligns with prior research on the "dark side" of WLB policies, which suggests that such initiatives may backfire by raising expectations or creating additional burdens for employees (Perrigino et al., 2018; Haines et al., 2024). Thus, the present study is best positioned as an exploratory investigation shedding light on the unique dynamics of the high-demand luxury hospitality sector, rather than as a theoretical generalization strengthening Social Exchange Theory.

The Effect of Job Stress on Work-Life Balance

Job stress has a negative and significant effect on WLB. Work-related stress reduces employees' ability to balance work and personal life, especially for those with family dependents (70.6% live with family). The highest stress indicator is mental fatigue (JS1: 2.38/5). This finding is in line with the study by (Urba & Soetjningsih, 2022), which stated that job stress has a significant negative effect on work-life balance. In the study

by (Liu et al., 2019), it was mentioned that job stress can reduce the ability to separate work and family roles.

The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Work-Life Balance

POS has a positive and significant effect on WLB. Organizational support, such as flexible policies and appreciation, helps employees manage work and family demands. The highest WLB indicator is the influence of personal life on work (WLB2: 3.88/5). These findings are consistent with previous studies conducted by (Fitria & Linda, 2019; Puspitasari & Ratnaningsih, 2019), which stated that perceived organizational support has a significant positive effect on work-life balance.

The Mediating Role of Work-Life Balance between Job Stress and Turnover Intention

WLB does not mediate the effect of job stress on turnover intention. Employees tend to consider leaving due to job stress regardless of their work-life balance. This is related to their productive age (31–40 years) and long tenure (49% >7 years). The hospitality industry is characterized by highly dynamic job demands, with heavy workloads, irregular working hours, and intense customer interactions. These conditions drive a direct path from stress to turnover intentions, as employees often lack the space or capacity to balance their work and personal life roles. Although some WLB policies are implemented, real-world practices show that fluctuating schedules and the need for 24-hour service limit the effectiveness of WLB as a buffer against stress. This situation contrasts with other sectors, such as banking or technology companies, where flexible schedules are easier to implement and have a more positive impact on work-life balance. In the hospitality sector, customer satisfaction and service quality are the primary performance indicators. The pressure to consistently deliver excellent service often leads employees to overlook available WLB programs, thereby weakening WLB's influence in reducing turnover intentions. Most employees are within the productive age range (31–40 years), have family responsibilities, and relatively long tenures. For this group, WLB can actually provide the space to evaluate career opportunities outside the company, which explains the positive relationship between WLB and turnover intentions found in this study.

According to a literature review conducted by (Rathi & Kumar, 2022), when employees are under continuous pressure for an extended period, it can lead to poor and impulsive decision-making. A relatively long tenure may cause employees to doubt the effectiveness of work-life balance improvements at PRQ Apartment, making them more likely to choose to leave the company. These results are not in line with previous studies, which showed that when the level of work-life balance is high, turnover intentions tend to be low (Mulang, 2022; Putri, 2024).

The Mediating Role of Work-Life Balance between Perceived Organizational Support and Turnover Intention

Perceived organizational support and its effect on turnover intention. The organizational support perceived by PRQ Apartment employees not only directly reduces their intention to leave but also does so indirectly by improving their work-life balance. When employees feel supported by the company through fairness, supervisor care, appropriate compensation, and supportive working conditions, they are better able to balance work demands and personal life. This finding supports the Social Exchange Theory (SET), which views social interaction as a reciprocal exchange between employees and the organization or among employees themselves (Cropanzano et al., 2017). The support provided by the organization is seen as a 'positive attitude' from the company that helps employees manage both work and personal life demands more effectively. In return, employees tend to be more focused and loyal in their work. Perceived organizational support creates a sense of obligation (Haines et al., 2024), motivating employees to maintain their work-life balance and ultimately reducing their desire to leave. This finding is also consistent with previous research by (Fitria & Linda, 2019).

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, PRQ Apartment needs to adopt more targeted strategies to manage job stress and enhance the effectiveness of work-life balance (WLB) policies. First, the company can develop structured stress management programs, such as hosting monthly training sessions on stress management, mindfulness, and relaxation techniques with the support of industrial psychology practitioners. In addition, implementing an Employee Assistance Program (EAP) would provide free and confidential counseling services for employees dealing with work-related stress or personal issues. These strategies can be complemented by a job rotation system and short micro-breaks during peak hours to reduce fatigue.

In terms of WLB policies, flexible scheduling should be strengthened, particularly for employees with family responsibilities. For example, providing more stable shifts and allowing scheduled shift swaps can help employees better balance work and family demands. The company could also consider offering direct support such as childcare subsidies, partnerships with local daycare centers, and more flexible family emergency leave. For employees with longer tenure or significant family obligations, options such as partial work hours or a four-day workweek during low season periods can serve as viable alternatives.

Furthermore, organizational support (POS) should be reinforced through performance- and loyalty-based recognition programs, along with regular one-on-one check-in sessions between supervisors and employees to assess workload, well-being, and career development plans. Leadership training is also essential to equip managers with the skills to provide consistent emotional and professional support. Additionally, regular monitoring through semi-annual stress and WLB surveys can serve as an evaluation tool to measure the effectiveness of these initiatives. To reduce turnover intentions driven by career stagnation, PRQ can establish a clear career development pathway, including internal promotion opportunities, cross-departmental training, and mentoring programs for new employees to help them adapt more quickly and manage workload effectively.

Research Limitations and Suggestions for Future Studies

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged when interpreting the findings. First, another critical limitation lies in the insufficient sample size ($n = 51$) for a PLS-SEM model with four constructs and one mediation path. Although PLS-SEM is relatively tolerant of smaller samples, this number falls below even the most lenient “10-times rule.” Consequently, the statistical power is drastically reduced, the risk of Type II error is heightened, and the stability of the model becomes questionable. The low R^2 values, particularly for turnover intention, directly reflect this limitation.

Second, the study’s focus on a single location, namely the PRQ Apartment in Surabaya, restricts the ability to generalize the findings to other organizations or industries. Variations in organizational culture, management practices, and workload patterns across different hospitality businesses could lead to different outcomes in the relationship between job stress, work-life balance (WLB), and turnover intentions.

Third, the reliance on self-reported survey data introduces the potential for common method bias (CMB), as both independent and dependent variables were collected from the same source at the same point in time. Although the questionnaire was validated and carefully designed to minimize bias, future studies could strengthen internal validity by incorporating multi-source data, such as supervisor assessments or objective HR performance and turnover records.

For future research, it is recommended to expand the scope of the study to include multiple hospitality organizations across different locations or cities to improve external validity. Increasing the sample size would also enhance the reliability and accuracy of statistical analyses, particularly in examining mediating or moderating effects. Additionally, future studies could employ a longitudinal research design to observe the dynamics of job stress, organizational support, and turnover intentions over time, thereby reducing temporal bias. Finally, integrating other relevant variables, such as burnout, job embeddedness, or emotional exhaustion, as mediating or moderating factors, could provide a deeper understanding of the mechanisms linking job stress, WLB, and turnover intentions within the hospitality industry.

Conclusion

This study provides deeper insights into the dynamics of job stress, perceived organizational support (POS), work-life balance (WLB), and turnover intentions in the hospitality sector, with a specific focus on PRQ Apartment in Surabaya. The findings reveal that job stress has a significant positive effect on turnover intentions, while POS has a significant negative effect, indicating that strong organizational support can effectively reduce employees’ intentions to leave. Meanwhile, WLB partially mediates

the relationship between POS and turnover intentions but does not mediate the effect of job stress on turnover intentions.

From a practical standpoint, the findings provide strategic guidance for PRQ Apartment in developing more targeted employee retention programs. To mitigate turnover driven by job stress, management should implement structured stress management initiatives, such as regular stress management training, confidential employee counseling through an Employee Assistance Program (EAP), and fairer shift rotations to prevent fatigue. Strengthening organizational support (POS) is equally critical; this could include enhancing performance-based reward systems, conducting regular one-on-one check-ins between supervisors and employees, and providing leadership training to help managers offer better emotional and professional support.

Rather than claiming to strengthen Social Exchange Theory, the main contribution of this study lies in offering exploratory evidence of the complex and non-linear relationship between WLB and turnover intention in the demanding context of luxury hospitality. Given the limited sample size, the study should be understood as an illustrative case that opens avenues for further research, rather than as strong theoretical confirmation.

In light of the critical limitation concerning sample size, the results of this study should be interpreted with caution. Rather than claiming to strengthen Social Exchange Theory, the findings are better positioned as exploratory insights that open avenues for further validation. Future research should employ substantially larger samples (e.g., $n > 150-200$) across multiple hospitality organizations to improve statistical robustness, enhance generalizability, and provide stronger empirical support for theoretical contributions.

For future research, a longitudinal design is recommended to observe the dynamics of job stress, POS, WLB, and turnover intentions over time. Additionally, multi-location comparisons involving hotels or apartments in other cities would strengthen external validity and reveal contextual factors that may influence the relationships observed in this study. Incorporating objective HR data, such as attendance, performance, and actual turnover records, could also help minimize perception bias and enhance the accuracy of future analyses.

References

- Agarwal, V., Mathiyazhagan, K., Malhotra, S., & Saikouk, T. (2022). Analysis of challenges in sustainable human resource management due to disruptions by Industry 4.0: An emerging economy perspective. *International Journal of Manpower*, 43(2), 513–541. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-03-2021-0192>
- Ahn, J. Y., & Chaoyu, W. (2019). Job stress and turnover intention revisited: Evidence from Korean firms. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 17(4), 52–61. [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.17\(4\).2019.05](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.17(4).2019.05)
- Belete, A. K. (2018). Turnover Intention Influencing Factors of Employees: An Empirical Work Review. *Journal of Entrepreneurship & Organization Management*, 07(03). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2169-026X.1000253>

- Chen, Y., Xia, P., Liu, C., Ye, C., Zeng, Q., & Liang, B. (2024). A chain mediation model on organizational support and turnover intention among healthcare workers in Guangdong province, China. *Frontiers in Public Health*, *12*.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1391036>
- Cropanzano, R., Anthony, E. L., Daniels, S. R., & Hall, A. V. (2017). Social Exchange Theory: A Critical Review with Theoretical Remedies. *Academy of Management Annals*, *11*(1), 479–516. <https://doi.org/10.5465/annals.2015.0099>
- Davies, A. C. L. (2022). Stress at work: Individuals or structures? *Industrial Law Journal*, *51*(2), 403–434. <https://doi.org/10.1093/indlaw/dwab006>
- Fitria, Y., & Linda, M. R. (2019). *Perceived Organizational Support and Work Life Balance on Employee Turnover Intention*. 503–506.
<https://doi.org/10.2991/icebef-18.2019.107>
- Haines, V. Y., Guerrero, S., & Marchand, A. (2024). Flexible work arrangements and employee turnover intentions: Contrasting pathways. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, *35*(11), 1970–1995.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2024.2323510>
- Hair, J., Hollingsworth, C. L., Randolph, A. B., & Chong, A. Y. L. (2022). An updated and expanded assessment of PLS-SEM in information systems research. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, *117*(3), Article 3.
- Jaharuddin, N., & Zainol, L. (2019). The Impact of Work-Life Balance on Job Engagement and Turnover Intention. *The South East Asian Journal of Management*, *13*(1). <https://doi.org/10.21002/seam.v13i1.10912>
- Li, Q., Mohamed, R., Mahomed, A., & Khan, H. (2022). The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support and Employee Care on Turnover Intention and Work Engagement: A Mediated Moderation Model Using Age in the Post Pandemic Period. *Sustainability*, *14*(15), Article 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14159125>
- Liu, J., Zhu, B., Wu, J., & Mao, Y. (2019). Job satisfaction, work stress, and turnover intentions among rural health workers: A cross-sectional study in 11 western provinces of China. *BMC Family Practice*, *20*(1), 9.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-019-0904-0>
- Mulang, H. (2022). Analysis of The Effect of Organizational Justice, Worklife Balance on Employee Engagement and Turnover Intention. *Golden Ratio of Human Resource Management*, *2*(2), 86–97. <https://doi.org/10.52970/grhrm.v2i2.169>
- Perrigino, M. B., Dunford, B. B., & Wilson, K. S. (2018). Work–Family Backlash: The “Dark Side” of Work–Life Balance (WLB) Policies. *Academy of Management Annals*, *12*(2), 600–630. <https://doi.org/10.5465/annals.2016.0077>
- Puspita, D. S., Haziroh, A. L., Mahmud, M., & Wardhani, M. F. (2024). Upaya Penurunan Turnover Intention Melalui Perceived Organizational Support, Career

- Development, Dan Work Life Balance Pada Karyawan Generasi Z Bank Bumh Di Kota Semarang. *Master: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis Terapan*, 4(1), 66–79. <https://doi.org/10.30595/jmbt.v4i1.23846>
- Puspitasari, K. A., & Ratnaningsih, I. Z. (2019). Hubungan antara Perceived Organizational Support Dengan Work-Life Balance pada Karyawan PT. BPR Kusuma Sumbing di Jawa Tengah. *Jurnal EMPATI*, 8(1), 82–86. <https://doi.org/10.14710/empati.2019.23578>
- Putri, N. L. P. S. A. D. P. (2024). Implikasi Work Life Balance dan Pengembangan Karir Terhadap Turnover Intention Karyawan di Grand Mirage Resort & Thalasso Bali. *GANEC SWARA*, 18(3), 1265. <https://doi.org/10.35327/gara.v18i3.935>
- Rathi, S., & Kumar, P. (2022). Job stress: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Health Sciences*, 6204–6222. <https://doi.org/10.53730/ijhs.v6nS6.10971>
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2015). *Organizational behavior* (16th ed.). New Jersey: Pearson Education.
- Rothbard, N. P., Beetz, A. M., & Harari, D. (2021). Balancing the Scales: A Configurational Approach to Work-Life Balance. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 8(Volume 8, 2021), 73–103. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-012420-061833>
- Salama, W., Abdou, A. H., Mohamed, S. A. K., & Shehata, H. S. (2022). Impact of Work Stress and Job Burnout on Turnover Intentions among Hotel Employees. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(15), Article 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19159724>
- Salvador, M., Moreira, A., & Pitacho, L. (2022). Perceived Organizational Culture and Turnover Intentions: The Serial Mediating Effect of Perceived Organizational Support and Job Insecurity. *Social Sciences*, 11(8), Article 8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci11080363>
- Sangadji, E. M. (2020). The effect of job stress on turnover intention through job satisfaction of government commercial bank employees. *KnE Social Sciences*, 66–82. <https://doi.org/DOI 10.18502/kss.v4i9.7317>
- Santos, J. A. A., & Labrague, L. J. (2021). The impact of fear of COVID-19 on job stress, and turnover intentions of frontline nurses in the community: A cross-sectional study in the Philippines. *Traumatology*, 27(1), 52. <https://doi.org/10.1037/trm0000294>
- Satardien, M., Jano, R., & Mahembe, B. (2019). The relationship between perceived organisational support, organisational commitment and turnover intention among employees in a selected organisation in the aviation industry. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 17. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajhrm.v17i0.1123>

- Sugiyono. (2021). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, Dan R&D*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta.
- Sulistiyani, E., Hidayat, Y. A., Setiawan, A., & Suwardi, S. (2022). Perceived organizational support, employee work engagement and work life balance: Social exchange theory perspective. *Jurnal Riset Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 15(2), 133–143. <https://doi.org/10.26623/jreb.v15i2.5336>
- Suswati, E. (2020). The Influence of Work Stress on Turnover Intention: Employee Performance as Mediator in Casual-Dining Restaurant. *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 18(2), 391–399. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.jam.2020.018.02.20>
- Takaya, R., Arsil, & Ramli, A. H. (2020). *Perceived Organizational Support and Turnover Intention*. 59–63. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.200915.015>
- Tang, G., Yu, B., Cooke, F. L., & Chen, Y. (2017). High-performance work system and employee creativity: The roles of perceived organisational support and devolved management. *Personnel Review*, 46(7), 1318–1334. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-09-2016-0235>
- Tsen, M. K., Gu, M., Tan, C. M., & Goh, S. K. (2021). Does flexible work arrangements decrease or increase turnover intention? A comparison between the social exchange theory and border theory. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 42(11–12), 962–983. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSSP-08-2021-0196>
- Urba, M. A., & Soetjningsih, C. H. (2022). Hubungan antara work life balance dan stres kerja pada karyawan. *Bulletin of Counseling and Psychotherapy*, 4(3), 694–700. <https://doi.org/10.51214/bocp.v4i3.383>
- Wong, Y.-W., & Wong, Y. (2017). The effects of perceived organisational support and affective commitment on turnover intention: A test of two competing models. *Journal of Chinese Human Resource Management*, 8(1), 2–21. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCHRM-01-2017-0001>
- Yıldırım, D., & Darıcan, Ş. (2024). The Effect of Perceived Social Support on Work-Life Balance and Work Engagement: A Case of Banking Sector. *Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 22(52), Article 52. <https://doi.org/10.35408/comuybd.1422526>
- Yuliana, L., Azmy, A., Nurwardana, J. R., Perkasa, D. H., Alfian, R., Aisah, N., & Putra, M. F. R. (2025). The Impact of Work Stress and Job Burnout on Turnover Intention among Indonesia-China Integrated Industrial Employees. *Journal of Applied Business Administration*, 9(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.30871/jaba.v9i1.8108>

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2025 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	The image shows the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license logo, which consists of two circular icons: one with 'cc' and another with a person icon, followed by the letters 'BY'.
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Widiyasa, M. S. S. A. and Suhermin, S. (2025). The Role of Work–Life Balance in Linking Stress, Support, and Turnover Intentions in Hospitality Industry. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 12 (11), 1720-1746. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2025.539824.1832</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_230523.html</p>	A square QR code is located in the bottom right corner of the table, which likely links to the full article or the journal's website.